

From online testament to digital zombie

Condensed version of the study, "La mort à l'ère numérique"

TA-SWISS, the Foundation for Technology Assessment and a centre for excellence of the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences, deals with the opportunities and risks of new technologies.

The report, "Death in the Digital Age", was prepared in an interdisciplinary collaboration between ethix – Lab for Innovation Ethics, University of Lausanne; the Lausanne University Hospital (CHUV); and the School of Engineering and Management (HEIG-VD), under the leadership of Jean-Daniel Strub, co-founder and director of ethix. The methodological concept of the study was based on comprehensive analyses of the existing scientific literature; Internet research on existing digital afterlife services; and qualitative interviews with users of existing services and with the developers of those services. In addition, a workshop was organised with international specialists who deal with aspects of death and changing death rituals from a scientific perspective – especially in the fields of sociology, philosophy and psychology. In the framework of a focus group, interviews were carried out with people who have experienced bereavement and mourning. To accompany the study, an analysis of the legal aspects of the digital afterlife was carried out by Nula Frei, Petru Zlatescu and Robert Naedele, Uni-Distance Suisse.

Condensed version of the study, "La mort à l'ère numérique"

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Death in the digital age – a brief overview

The more frequently and intensively we use mobile phones, tablets and other networked devices, the greater the digital footprint we leave online. What happens to these digital traces when we die? Due to the widespread use of social media, this question is becoming all the more urgent: by 2100, for example, it is likely that the profiles on Facebook that belong to deceased users will exceed the number of living users.

In the past few years, an increasing number of companies have come onto the market which provide digital inheritance planning and management services. These companies can be classified into two groups: in one group, the companies enable their clientele to specify what happens to their personal data when they die. This may concern the safe-keeping of their passwords so that their heirs can readily memorialise online accounts or definitively delete the deceased's personal data (e-mails, etc.). In the other group, companies enable their clientele to supply audio recordings or videos that can be listened to or viewed as of a specified date. Services designed to regulate the management of a person's own digital inheritance are provided by companies in the so-called "death tech" segment, while those in the other group provide their services to mourners, which include the possibility of establishing virtual memorials on the Internet. They can also use a deceased's personal data in order to programme a chat robot ("deadbot") that emulates the deceased's personality, or to create an avatar that simulates ongoing contact with the deceased's relatives. These are referred to as "grief tech" services.

Opportunities ...

For people who are nearing the end of their life and have to prepare for their passing, a "digital testament" can bring peace of mind in that they clearly specify what is to be done with their personal digital data.

A well-planned inheritance also helps survivors cope with bereavement, because additional bureaucracy can make mourning even more difficult if access to the deceased's e-mail or social media accounts remains blocked due to the unavailability of the necessary passwords.

With virtual memorials it is also possible to include distant living relatives and friends in the collective mourning process.

... Risks ...

If deceased persons continue to "exist" in the form of chat robots or avatars over an extended period of time, this can make the final stage of the mourning process – acceptance – even more difficult for the survivors.

If the stored personal data of deceased persons should be lost, for example due to technical problems or a company closure, for the survivors this could result in a "second loss" experience that could be traumatic.

For survivors, it is also distressing if the personal data of their deceased relatives or friends should be hacked and manipulated with the aid of image generation software – especially if the deceased person speaks and acts in a faked video in an entirely uncharacteristic manner.

... And a few recommendations

Awareness of the necessity and possibility of digital inheritance planning is an integral part of digital literacy. Corresponding campaigns and information events should therefore be carried out.

Everyone should be able to have all their digital traces erased. In addition, survivors should be able to refuse to receive messages or other digital legacies from deceased persons.

In order to ensure that people's right to self-determination and the protection of their data can be assured after their passing, information and sensitisation campaigns should be carried out that explain the applicable legal framework and the formal legal requirements for rulings in the event of death, including in a digital context. These campaigns should be conceived for testators and survivors, as well as for specialists who deal with all issues relating to dying and death.

A final resting place in the digital afterlife

Digitalisation is increasingly penetrating our daily life, and is also changing processes relating to dying and coping with grief. The Covid-19 pandemic gave rise to an additional boost in the online exchange of personal data. A dynamic business field has evolved that focuses on the digital legacy of deceased persons.

When people die, they leave all sorts of traces behind: clothing that is no longer required, all kinds of household goods, assets and jewellery, perhaps correspondence and diaries. But alongside these material goods, people are now also leaving behind a constantly increasing immaterial legacy in the form of personal data. This includes e-mails, WhatsApp and Instagram accounts, various online subscriptions, blog posts, photos in the social media, videos on YouTube, recorded messages on answering machines, etc.

From grave to profile graveyard

A variety of instruments are available for managing the inheritance of material goods. Inheritance law stipulates how these goods have to be distributed, and the responsibilities of the relevant authorities are also clearly defined.

By contrast, the relatives and friends of the deceased are often confused and overwhelmed when it comes to handling the personal data that have been left behind. Unless they possess the necessary access details and passwords for the various accounts, it is almost impossible for them to update

or delete the data or profiles within a reasonable timeframe. Furthermore, unless they are copyright protected and thus have a material value, the data and accounts do not form part of the deceased's estate. And this is becoming an ever more serious problem: it is anticipated that the number of profiles on Facebook belonging to deceased users will reach around 4.9 billion by 2100, and will therefore exceed the number of living users. This also applies to other social media platforms.

Covid-19 as driving force behind virtual contact

With the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, the volume of personal data on the Internet rose drastically. Numerous activities that had previously taken place in direct interpersonal contact were carried out online during the lockdowns. School lessons, lectures and meetings were held via video conference software and many of these were recorded. Nursing and retirement homes, which during peak periods of the pandemic prohibited visits even from immediate family members, provided their patients and residents with tablets in order to enable them to at least keep in touch with their loved ones via the Internet. Funeral and church services were also transmitted via digital media.

The extent to which the Covid-19 pandemic changed our habits is illustrated by the figures published by the global database, Statista: whereas in January 2020 the Zoom app – cloud video-conferencing software – was downloaded solely via Apple

Store 840,000 times prior to the outbreak of the pandemic, in April that same year the number of downloads increased by a factor of more than forty to almost 36 million. This means that numerous people who had in the past mainly encountered one another face to face now grew accustomed to establishing contact online.

Digital planning, assistance for mourners

Personal data stored on the Internet and in cloud services can cause problems for survivors, but under certain circumstances can also provide assistance for mourners. Digital planning services can help the (still) living with the problems associated with online personal data, in particular in the context of access to orphaned accounts. Here, applications are available that make it possible to save access information and a kind of testament for handling personal data. Specialists refer to these as “death tech” services. In the same way as in the real world, advance regulation of the estate simplifies at least the administration of death in the virtual world.

But the data left behind by a deceased person can also support grieving survivors. For example, it is possible that their grief could be mitigated if they were able to view images of a deceased loved-one from happy times, or if a video recalls to mind the endearing quirks of their late father. Specialists refer to the use of data in the context of coping with bereavement as “grief tech”. The TA-SWISS study distinguishes between “death tech” and “grief tech” services; together, these two fields of study form what is referred to as the “digital afterlife”, i.e. the active and passive digital presence of people after their death.

Technology as a bridge to the afterlife

When they are confronted with the immaterial traces of deceased persons, survivors react in different ways. While some dial the deceased person’s phone number so that they can hear his/her voice again via voicemail, others find posthumous messages disturbing. The inspiration for Stephen King’s novella, “Mr. Harrigan’s Phone”, apparently came when he heard the voice of a deceased friend on voicemail – an occurrence that he says upset him for quite some time. This short story describes how a mobile phone that was secretly placed inside Mr. Harrigan’s coffin established a frightening connection between life and the afterlife.

In earlier times too, people considered how new technologies could be used for creating a passage into the realm of the dead. When US Congress approved a credit line of 30,000 dollars in 1843 for an initial telegraph line between Baltimore and Washington, a petition containing 13,000 signatures was submitted to the Senate calling for it to consider the possibility of a “spiritual telegraph line” between heaven and earth. However, the senators voted to ignore the petition.

Numerous developments in a new field of activity

The challenges that arise relating to the data traces of deceased persons are clearly apparent. It is by no means only the relatives of deceased persons who find themselves confronted with the problem of profile and data “graveyards”. To an increasing extent, social media and other platform operators also have to find solutions, along with other economic stakeholders.

As the technological possibilities are undergoing rapid development, services are being adapted at a fast pace. In view of the momentum in the areas of death tech and grief tech, estimating the developments in the foreseeable future is a demanding task. The following chapter deals with the economic stakeholders and associated potentials.

Death tech and grief tech services from the perspective of the providers

Digital afterlife providers offer a broad range of products and services. In addition to conventional service providers such as undertakers, psychologists offering grief counselling and notary offices, an increasing number of startups are now also providing services directly to the involved persons – in particular, survivors – focusing on the personal data of the deceased.

Generally speaking, when a new company is founded, its main focus is on financial objectives. Its aim is to maximise profit or at least generate revenue that covers its costs. In the surveys that were carried out within the scope of the TA-SWISS study, however, the founders of digital afterlife services cited other primary motivations.

Many of them stated that a personal experience had prompted them to establish a digital planning or online grief tech platform: in their statements they explained, for example, that an accident had opened their eyes to the fact that their immediate relatives and close friends would by no means find it easy to access important documents and digital accounts. Others who had unexpectedly been afflicted by a serious illness grew aware of what information they would have wished to pass on to their loved ones – and this motivated them to develop a platform for communicating final audio or written messages to surviving relatives. Other respondents stated that the sudden death of a relative or friend prompted them to establish a virtual memorial.

Four targeted digital afterlife services ...

In line with the scientific literature, the TA-SWISS study designates four categories of service providers whose business models focus on the data of deceased persons:

- a) Companies that provide digital planning services and which in accordance with the terminology of specialists are active in the field of death tech services;
- b) Providers of death tech services that enable people to store messages that can be passed on to survivors at a specified point in time;
- c) Remembrance platforms on which survivors can set up a virtual memorial in order to preserve the memory of a deceased person; these platforms thus provide grief tech services;
- d) Companies that provide a continued digital existence after death and which are active in the grief tech segment. They use the stored data of deceased persons in order to create chatbots – which in the context of coping with grief are referred to as “deadbots” – or avatars of those persons, and thus to “breathe life” into them with the aid of artificial intelligence. This enables survivors to maintain virtual contact with their deceased loved ones, chat with them or even “meet” them in the realm of virtual reality using data goggles.

... plus non-specific applications

The market is determined to an equal extent, however, by supply and demand. Those who use a given service help shape a corresponding business field. Here it is apparent that many people use a social media platform as an instrument for coping with grief and as a location for memorials – although these platforms were not originally designed for these purposes. Thus Facebook and other social media platforms also play a significant role in the digital afterlife.

In 2009, Facebook’s parent company, Meta, introduced the possibility of memorialising a person’s account. Those who wish to do this must prove that they are immediate family members or have been appointed to minister the deceased person’s estate. They also have to provide a scan or photo of the death certificate. In this way, the content that people have uploaded to their Facebook account during their lifetime remains online and can continue to be viewed by anyone who previously had access to the account. However, no new followers can be linked to this type of profile. Other social media platforms (e.g., Instagram, LinkedIn) also offer the option of a remembrance profile or enable the accounts of deceased persons to be erased.

Current “map” of digital afterlife services

The study conducted by TA-SWISS cites more than 60 examples of digital afterlife applications and services, and locates them on a digital afterlife “map” with a description of their most important features. The list includes all services domiciled in Switzerland at the time the study was prepared; most of the other examples were located in European countries, while 16 cited were based in the USA or other countries outside Europe.

In the above paragraph, the past tense has been used in view of the fast growth in the field of digital afterlife services and the foreseeable rapid changes: a British analysis of the digital afterlife revealed that more than half of the identified services disappeared within six years or remained inactive for longer than a year during the assessment period. And a number of the providers questioned in the TA-SWISS study stated that they had either discontinued their digital afterlife service activities or intended to sell their company. It is therefore difficult to estimate both the economic potential of digital afterlife services and the extent to which customers are likely to use them.

Combining the conventional and the innovative

Within the scope of their professional activities, care specialists and psychologists, who have always provided end-of-life and bereavement support, undertakers, who take care of the deceased, and notaries, who assist the survivors, are aware of the growing influence of death tech and grief tech services. In some cantons, professional associations of notaries have already issued fact sheets on the topic of digital inheritance.

On the other hand, numerous digital platforms are encroaching on the area of activity of conventional funeral services in that they also plan and organise funerals. Other platforms mediate psychologists upon request for counselling, and are thus becoming active in the field of psychological support. In the long term, in the area of death and mourning it is to be expected that conventional analogue and new digital services will merge.

Uncertain market development

Everyone must die, and this means that a correspondingly large market can be anticipated for digital inheritance planning and remembrance culture. But from the survey of providers of these services it is clear that the already existing companies are a long way from reaching their potential clientele. One study estimates that the global market potential of all services associated with death, including digital afterlife services, is around 120 billion US dollars a year. And the predictions are impressive too: the same study anticipates annual growth rates of six percent up to 2030.

Whether digital afterlife services will be able to keep pace with the predicted growth rate remains to be seen. Although a large number of startups have ventured into this field, the volume of investments remains below expectations. In the view of industry insiders, this is attributable to the fact that many players shy away from the notion of “profiting from death”.

No services in Switzerland for creating a lasting digital presence of a deceased person

The services provided by companies domiciled in Switzerland all share one clear feature: none of them can be used to create a lasting digital presence of a deceased person with the aid of a deadbot or avatar. Those services often originate in the USA and South Korea and are frequently the focus of media attention even though in practice they are (still) relatively little used.

In 2020, an experiment carried out by the South Korean TV channel, MBC, caused a worldwide sensation. MBC arranged for the creation of an avatar of Na-Yeons, a seven-year-old girl who had died of leukaemia. This enabled her mother to encounter her in virtual reality, and thanks to the use of data goggles and a glove she was also able to interact with her. This reunion in the digital realm of the afterlife had required an enormous amount of effort. It took the Korean laboratory a total of eight months to transform Na-Yeon’s face, body and voice from past images and recordings into a virtual avatar. MBC broadcast a documentary of the experiment and triggered a wave of sympathy throughout

the country. A video presenting an approximately nine-minute extract from the broadcast was posted on YouTube. It was viewed more than forty million times and became an Internet hit.

By contrast, the majority of services in Switzerland focus on digital inheritance planning and virtual

remembrance platforms. Two companies offer the posthumous transmission of deceased persons' messages. Thus the services provided in Switzerland appear relatively conservative compared to those on offer in South Korea and the USA – an indication that dealing with the afterlife reflects societal, religious and cultural influences.

Variety of digital afterlife services for a diverse clientele

The companies placed on the “digital afterlife map” offer a broad variety of services: their clientele can decide whether they want to safely deposit their data or if they wish to place them at the disposal of their survivors in order to maintain contact. Here, various technical issues still have to be clarified.

Few people are willing to address the matter of their own death. A study on inheritance planning carried out by the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW) in 2023 found that around 1,700 of the respondents over the age of 40 defer their inheritance planning for a lengthy period of time. Nevertheless, around 52 percent of the respondents stated that they had planned their inheritance. Something that causes internal resistance in the real world is hardly made any easier in the virtual sphere.

Consequences of lack of digital inheritance planning

The number of people who surf on the Internet, communicate via e-mail and use a Facebook or Instagram account but do not make any preparations for their digital inheritance, is probably very high.

This means that all those who should be able to manage a digital legacy after someone close to them has died, cannot do so because they do not have access to any of the stored data. In a worst-case scenario they could unexpectedly stumble upon digital traces of a deceased friend or relative, triggering renewed grief – for example, if they receive a notification from Facebook reminding them of the deceased user's birthday.

Digital archive for personal data

It is primarily people who are experienced in the use of the virtual realm and are able to quickly adopt technological innovations who think about digital inheritance planning. For the survivors of these “early adopters” the situation is clearly regulated, and thanks to the access granted to them they are able to ensure that the deceased's orphaned social media accounts can be transferred into remembrance status. In this way, an unexpected – and unwanted – encounter with the deceased's digital traces can be avoided.

The homepage of one Swiss provider draws attention to the close relationship between deceased persons and their survivors: on the one hand, in addition to storing access information pertaining to their digital data on the platform, customers can also provide emergency medical information and instructions for administrative tasks. Users can even plan their own funeral via this company. On the other hand, their designated representative is given direct access to the uploaded data, as well as to a checklist that takes them step-by-step through the difficult stages following the person's death or in the case of an emergency.

Digital inheritance planning is meanwhile equivalent to a will. The content must be presented on paper, and the document has to be personally signed by the testator. Thus the applicable formal requirements for wills have not been adapted to the digital sphere.

Collective mourning online

Almost nowhere evokes the memory of deceased persons as strongly as their final resting place. A variety of services offer the possibility of storing texts, audio recordings, photos, etc., on a platform. Thanks to geolocation technology, or with the aid of a transmitter discreetly placed on a gravestone or at another location that is meaningful for the involved persons, visitors can receive and view the saved data on their mobile device by scanning a QR code using a mobile app. "Sharing means immortalising" is the slogan of a company that provides such a service. Survivors are able to share available content online, though only if they are in the vicinity of the deceased's gravestone or a specified memorial location.

Other services waive the use of geolocation. Their memorials are located exclusively on the Internet, where a biography of the deceased person, or audio recordings and videos, can be uploaded. The length of the deceased's life story depends on the selected tariff, and it is often the case that cheaper versions only permit the use of black-and-white images.

Some of these platforms focus on collective mourning. Under the motto, "Mourning needs to be shared", with the aid of an algorithm a German platform brings people together who find themselves in a similar situation and can jointly mourn their loss.

Birthday greetings from beyond the grave

There are also people who want to posthumously maintain some form of contact with their relatives and friends. They can leave a message behind to be delivered during the wedding of a grandchild, for example, or on another important family occasion. "Participate in mourning the loss of your loved ones" is the slogan of one provider in Switzerland, who offers the possibility of recording video or text messages that can be played back to commemorate a particularly important occasion in the course of the deceased person's life.

Other providers focus exclusively on audio message services. An organisation that is financed via donations provides its services to people suffering from a fatal illness, in particular the parents of young children. It supplies the survivors with a heart-shaped USB stick on which the words of their loved ones are recorded.

Digital doubles

Various companies domiciled in the USA and South Korea produce digital doubles of people based on their personal data. One of these companies advertises the fact that, on the basis of a fully patented digital communication system, it is able to use artificial intelligence and machine learning in order to depict and emulate the relationship between mourners and the deceased through chats. According to this company, it is thus possible to establish authentic communication after a person's death. It has coined the term "versona" to designate its generated virtual versions of deceased persons.

A South Korean company wants to take things a step further than chats and the playback of audio recordings. It has issued a promotional video that shows how a mourning widow encounters and chats with the digital double of her deceased husband. This involves the projection of videos that were recorded prior to a person's decease and at great expense. The videos are then combined with generative artificial intelligence, which is able to create new content on the basis of the deceased person's data. Here, even the deceased's facial expressions and lip movements are simulated. In this way, a kind of real-time communication is simulated between relatives and virtual doubles. This takes place in a specially equipped room on the company's premises and is extremely expensive. For the seven hours of video and audio recording that are required for the creation of the digital double, at least 10,000 dollars are budgeted, and each 30-minute encounter with the avatar costs a further 1,200 dollars. The disparity of access to digital afterlife services is one of the problems that arise from a societal and ethical perspective.

Various financing models

Very few services are financed via donations. Only one Swiss provider is financed in this way. Other platforms located in Switzerland usually apply varying tariffs. Basic services can be obtained free of charge. For other services, clients can choose between a monthly subscription and a lump-sum fee which secures them lifelong access to the platform without additional charges.

Some providers model their fees closely on those of conventional funeral services, and primarily use digital technologies in order to simplify associated services. These include the design of death notices and the organisation of funeral services. With some providers the transition between digital and real inheritance planning is seamless.

Secure storage of data

In practice, the provision of death tech and grief tech services has to overcome a variety of challenges. On the one hand, it is essential to ensure that unauthorised persons cannot access the digital inheritance, while on the other, designated representatives have to be able to access the data. The challenges associated with the storage of digital inheritance data are similar to those relating to electronic patient files. The fact that little progress has been made with the latter national project underscores the difficulties associated with the processing of sensitive data.

One of the distinguishing features of Internet and cloud-based services is that they transcend national borders. Providers of digital afterlife services also acquire their clientele on the international stage. However, the applicable legal provisions differ from country to country. In order to keep the processing of the data as uncomplicated as possible, it makes

sense to store them where the provider has its head office. This means that the operators of the servers, as well as the involved players or third parties who have access to the data, are subject to the same data protection provisions. Swiss providers of death tech services attach importance to storing users' data within Switzerland, because unlike the legal provisions in, for example, the USA, the applicable Swiss legislation largely protects personal data from access by the authorities and other third parties.

Digital inheritance planning would be made simpler if official documents could be validated electronically. With an officially recognised electronic proof of identity (e-ID) it would be possible to simplify dealings with the authorities in that users could identify themselves on digital platforms in a binding manner. Various platforms in the field of death tech offer services such as formulating a power of attorney. But this type of document can only be validated electronically if the applicant is able to provide reliable proof of identity. In the TA-SWISS study, various respondents stated that they were convinced that an e-ID would provide additional impetus to their services and thus enable them to expand their customer base.

Psychological pros and cons in the digital afterlife

Thanks to the availability of personal data stored in advance by deceased persons, survivors can take their leave of them in a more smoothly structured manner: photos, videos and personal posts left behind by deceased persons evoke vivid memories of them. If a deceased person remains present in the everyday life of the living, this can harbour both opportunities and risks.

Contact via digital means cannot substitute direct interpersonal exchange. But when the latter is not possible, virtual contact can be comforting. To quote one of the members of the TA-SWISS study focus group: "There is nothing more extraordinary than being present during someone's final minutes, being able to physically comfort them, embrace them, hold their hand. But if this is no longer possible, then some digital tools are truly fantastic."

Overcoming physical distances

In the digital sphere, grief can be shared anywhere. During the travel restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the possibility for survivors living a long way away from the deceased to participate online in the funeral service proved to be consoling for a great many people. Sharing grief online can strengthen the bonds between relatives and friends wherever they may be.

Memorials in the virtual sphere can be viewed at any time and from anywhere, as long as an Internet connection is available. For people who shy away from visiting an actual cemetery, an online memorial represents low-threshold access to a remembrance site. Members of the younger generations in particular have no difficulty in looking back online on experiences with deceased persons and sharing their memories of these with others.

Presence on important occasions

When dying persons record messages for their relatives, this can ease their own pain as well as that of their survivors. Here, for example, people can congratulate their loved ones on an important occasion in their life and pass on their best wishes – a notion that enables them to deal with the fact that they will no longer be around when, for example, their daughter gets married or a grandchild passes an important exam.

But if the survivors receive such messages from someone who played an important role in their life in the past, this can also comfort them and give them encouragement for their future.

Changing attitude towards death and transience

The notion of keeping in contact with a loved one posthumously with the aid of technology may be comforting for some people, but this by no means applies to everyone. Those who withdraw into the virtual realm in order to cope with the death of a friend or relative run the risk of becoming isolated. In any case, people who use digital afterlife services report mixed experiences. While some state that they feel they belong to a community thanks to chats in Facebook groups or on virtual remembrance platforms, others who visit online grieving forums feel an increasing sense of loneliness and isolation.

Funeral service providers and church groups also fear that, if the use of digital services for coping with bereavement were to become prevalent, rituals could lose their meaning, and reverence for the dead could decline. Others predict that death rituals will continue to be performed, but that thanks to technological applications they will be experienced in different ways. The increasing options for dealing with dying and death could be applied at the expense of social cohesion.

Although the TA-SWISS study concludes that the technological options will not challenge our awareness of the finiteness of life, deepfakes – i.e. technologically manipulated or entirely synthetically generated films – in the form of a drama with a long-since deceased film star in the leading role, could nonetheless change the socially anchored notions of transience. TA-SWISS has carried out a separate study that specifically analyses the risks and opportunities associated with deepfakes.

In accordance with the current study, the place which deadbots and avatars will occupy within the scope of digital afterlife services will in any case reflect the level of social acceptance for the digitalisation of death.

Repeated loss, repeated mourning

Those who comfort themselves over the loss of a loved one by viewing digital images or chatting with an avatar generated by artificial intelligence – i.e. the “versona” of the deceased person – run the risk of having to mourn a second time if the corresponding data should be lost.

The fact that numerous providers of digital afterlife services will only exist for a relatively short time increases the risk of second loss. The data accrued in daily life pertaining to a deceased person can also be lost and thus distress survivors: here, for example, a deceased person’s recorded answerphone message is deleted as soon as his/her subscription has been cancelled.

In the literature, a case is cited in which someone received a reply to a text message he had sent to his deceased sister’s mobile phone. After a brief moment of hope that his sister was still alive, he realised that the phone number had already been allocated to a new user. He consequently had to mourn for a second time. Second loss is in contrast with the notion of digital immortality, which providers of digital afterlife services invoke in their advertising campaigns.

Ability to let go

Survivors can only successfully bring mourning to a close if they are able to take their leave of the deceased person and find a new self- and world-orientation. If deceased persons remain constantly present in digital form in the daily life of the living, this can hamper the successful conclusion of the mourning process.

But if the survivors succeed in harmonising the digital presence of a deceased person with the intensity of their own grief, then grief tech and death tech services, as well as social media, can be helpful. One of the members of the focus group spoke of the Facebook page she had created for her mother. In the first few months after her mother's death she visited the page frequently and felt comforted when she saw that friends also viewed the page and remembered her mother. But when the automated Facebook reminders – for example, about her mother's birthday or wedding anniversary – began to upset her, she decided to delete the profile.

Misuse of data

In the same way as with profiles of living people, those of deceased persons can become the target of hateful and disparaging posts. Social media platforms are crawling with trolls: in 2017 already, in a survey of adults in the USA, around 38 percent of the respondents stated that they came across posts from trolls in the social media almost daily. For survivors, malicious remarks can strengthen the pain of loss and the feeling of helplessness. In some cases this can prolong the period of mourning.

Furthermore, digital data can be easily copied and manipulated with the aid of image generation software. This means that, for the deceased, there is little certainty that the data they uploaded to their social media accounts will not be misused. The image of a deceased person can then be presented in a misleading context and he/she could appear to act or speak in an uncharacteristic manner. For the survivors, coming across such a video can be deeply upsetting and depressing.

High energy consumption

Although digital legacies are intangible, they nonetheless have an impact on the environment. Uploading and storing data requires a great deal of energy. If the use of digital afterlife services keeps growing in the future, this will result in a further increase in electricity demand.

The digital services sector accounts for around seven percent of global electricity consumption today, and it is estimated that its level of CO₂ emissions is between one and four percent of the total global volume of greenhouse gas emissions. Although death tech and grief tech applications only occupy a small niche within this sector, a close eye needs to be kept on energy consumption in the field of afterlife services. If deceased persons' data are stored online over a lengthy period of time, they become an ecological burden for future generations.

Need to find a balance in the legal and philosophical context between remembering and forgetting

Personal data can be manipulated relatively easily today. Survivors can benefit from legislation governing their personal rights and protection of their data, and thus defend themselves against misuse of their images and videos. For the deceased, however, other rules apply. But the applicable legislation contains loopholes which to date can only be addressed on a philosophical level.

In autumn 2019, a report from Hollywood caught the attention of film buffs, namely that James Dean had been nominated to play the leading role in the war drama, "Finding Jack". The intention here was to bring James Dean – who died in a car crash in 1955 at the age of 24 – back to the big screen with the aid of CGI (computer generated imagery) technology. The project was to be jointly realised by Magic City Films and Worldwide XR. The latter says it holds the rights to images and recordings of numerous celebrities. In addition to James Dean, the "Rights" section on its website lists celebrities such as dancer Josephine Baker, boxer Sugar Ray Robinson, pilot Amelia Earhart, plus countless other deceased legends from the fields of showbiz and sport.

Questions regarding the use of images of deceased persons

There is currently no sign of the announced war film, either at Magic City Films or Worldwide XR. The project is now less ambitious: the cinematic reanimation, "James Dean 2.0", will instead be used in a digital artwork – a so-called commemorative NFT (non-fungible token).

Projects of this nature raise questions regarding the protection of personal integrity and intellectual property rights. The rights to images of James Dean belong to his family, who have apparently assigned their use to Worldwide XR. But we will never know whether his posthumous appearance in a war drama or as the central figure in an artwork would have been in line with his wishes, or whether he would have perceived these projects as an inadmissible intrusion into his private sphere.

In the first half of the twentieth century, a posthumous appearance on a cinema screen would have been barely conceivable for an actor or actress. Today, those who have witnessed the current technological developments can take appropriate action. For example, Robin Williams – who died in August 2014 – stipulated that no images and recordings of him could be used during the next 25 years. This means that, for the foreseeable future, no one may create a hologram of a Robin Williams stand-up number or incorporate him digitally into a new film.

Reduced protection of personal integrity for deceased persons

While bringing celebrities back to life in digital form is the subject of headline news, this is in fact an issue that essentially concerns everyone in that it ultimately affects digital self-determination and respect for privacy. Article 13 of the Swiss Federal Constitution stipulates that everyone is entitled to protection of their private sphere and family life, their dwelling, and their mail and telecommunications, as well as to protection against the misuse of their personal data. But in accordance with Swiss legislation, these personal protection rights expire when the person dies.

This is not the case in some other countries (e.g. Germany), where personal rights are also protected posthumously. Here the principle applies that a personality is not extinguished when someone dies, and that interests worthy of protection continue to exist to which close relatives can refer. The latter can, for example, bring an action on behalf of the deceased. This is not possible in Switzerland, where only living persons can take legal action against an infringement of their personal rights. Thus survivors could consider the disrespectful treatment of a deceased person through defamation of character, for example, or the malicious defacement of their final resting place, as an infringement of their personal rights.

Question of protection of personal rights of the deceased

From a philosophical perspective, the question arises whether people can be deemed to continue to exist in some way in their virtual image so that a right to personal protection would also have to apply to their “persona”. Philosophers agree that a digitally generated image is not entitled to the same protection of personal rights as the original image of the living person.

Nonetheless, ethical obligations exist that require survivors to handle the deceased person’s data with due care and attention. Here, for example, they must ensure that in a digital image the deceased person’s identity, appearance and character traits are not significantly changed, rendered unrecognisable or otherwise transformed.

The negligent or improper use of a deceased person’s data intensifies the grief of the survivors. For this reason alone, some philosophers propose that the private sphere of deceased persons should be afforded a certain, albeit lesser, degree of legal protection. In addition, the desecration of graves and the dead is a crime, which is another reason for treating the personal data of the deceased with respect, because occurrences in the virtual realm cannot be considered separate from social relations and practices in the real world.

Interaction between data protection and inheritance law

There are still numerous legal issues relating to the data of deceased persons that are the subject of debate among specialists. Article 1 of the Federal Data Protection Ordinance, that was repealed on 1 September 2023, stipulated that information concerning the data of deceased persons had to be provided if the applicant was able to demonstrate a valid interest in the information and that no conflict with overriding interests existed on the part of relatives of the deceased person or third parties. The revised version of the Federal Data Protection Act, that entered into force in 2023, no longer contains provisions relating to the data of deceased persons. The reason given for this omission was that there is a close relationship between the personality of the deceased and the right to information. As a result, the former cannot be inherited. In addition, in the opinion of the legislator, the provisions of the Swiss

Civil Code adequately regulate relations between the deceased and their heirs. However, it does not contain any provisions concerning the personal data of deceased persons.

Items such as laptops, mobile phones and PCs which contain the deceased person’s data form part of the estate, so both the hardware and the data can be passed on to the heirs. However, the situation is different with respect to data that the deceased person had uploaded to platforms. Here, from the perspective of inheritance law, specialists tend to view mere access to an account – i.e. the possibility of reading the data – differently from its continued active use. Since it would be strange if survivors were to continue using the account in lieu of the deceased person, many specialists feel that only read rights should be inheritable, but not the full use of the account itself. Of course, the situation with respect to the accounts of influencers, with which revenue can be earned, needs to be clarified from the point of view of inheritance law. In such a case, a social media account could represent an asset that flows into the inheritance.

In the case of films featuring James Dean and the works of other creative artists, the issue of copyright law also has to be taken into account. Copyright law protects financial and personal interests in intellectual creations, i.e. all intellectual products with an individual character, in particular literary works, music compositions and photographs, as well as computer software. Protection normally lasts for up to 70 years after the death of the author/originator. Thereafter, anyone can publish, process and modify the images, audio recordings, videos and written works concerned. Copyrights form an integral part of a deceased person’s estate; the heirs take over ownership from the deceased person and represent the latter’s interests. Thus the heirs of James Dean can use photos of the film star as they wish and license a film production company to use the images for new projects.

Ten recommendations for planning digital inheritance

Many people are not aware of the extent to which a well-planned digital inheritance can help survivors cope with the various administrative tasks following a death. However, during the existential crisis at the end of a person's life it should always be possible to continue to use conventional analogue services.

Death in the digital age poses challenges not only for individuals, but also for service providers, public authorities and political bodies, all of whom are addressed in the recommendations of TA-SWISS.

Need for information and discussion

Most people are still unaware of the new digital afterlife services, and only very few think about what will happen to their personal data after their death. The population therefore needs to be sensitised to this issue: the requirements and options with respect to digital inheritance planning should be incorporated into campaigns to foster education on the use of digital technologies. It would also be important to determine how digital inheritance planning can be more effectively integrated into decision-making processes and end-of-life support.

Furthermore, public discussion should address the question whether the distribution of digital afterlife applications is desirable, especially those designed to bring about the virtual continuation of a deceased person in the form of an avatar or deadbot.

Need to ensure reliability and high quality

The personal data of the deceased are sensitive and survivors feel vulnerable. It is thus all the more important to ensure the protection and secure storage of such data. This means that the providers of digital afterlife services have to meet high quality standards in order to prevent misuse of the data.

In order to ensure that as many people as possible are able to benefit from the advantages of digital estate planning and the use of digital afterlife services, corresponding framework conditions should be created, such as suitable remuneration of the various services and electronic identification options for the users.

Need for both digital and conventional services

Grief tech applications can support mourners, but there are also people who feel lonelier and more depressed when they visit a virtual remembrance platform. In view of this, individual support for those who have difficulty in coping with the mourning process needs to be affordable and readily accessible.

Funeral service providers and grief counselling specialists should be capable of identifying (and thus avoiding) the risks associated with digital afterlife services: these include the risk of the survivor suffering a second period of mourning if the deceased's stored data should be lost, or the possibility that the mourning process could be prolonged if the deceased person remains present in digital form in the survivor's daily life.

Data and copyright protection for deceased persons

With the ongoing development of the various technologies, especially those based on generative artificial intelligence, it is foreseeable that personal data could be incorporated into the generation of avatars and deadbots to an increasing extent. Here the prerequisites have to be created for assuring the informed use of the applied technologies. In particular, campaigns should be implemented with the aim of informing people about their rights as (future) deceased persons or as relatives.

Because Swiss legislation does not contain any legal bases for the protection of the data of deceased persons, the legislator should be urged to create the necessary prerequisites for ensuring that everyone (including a deceased's heirs) is able to retain control of what happens to their personal data after their death.

Providers of digital afterlife services should also guarantee the right of erasure: everyone who wishes to do so should be able to have all their digital traces erased. In addition, all survivors should be able to refuse to receive messages or other digital legacies from deceased persons.

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Impressum

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Condensed version of the study, "La mort à l'ère numérique"

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New technology often leads to decisive improvements in the quality of our lives. At the same time, however, it involves new types of risks whose consequences are not always predictable. The Foundation for Technology Assessment TA-SWISS examines the potential advantages and risks of new technological developments in the fields of life sciences and medicine, digitalisation and society as well as energy and environment. The studies carried out by the Foundation are aimed at the decision-making bodies in politics and the economy, as well as at the general public. In addition, TA-SWISS promotes the exchange of information and opinions between specialists in science, economics and politics and the public at large through participatory processes. Studies conducted and commissioned by the Foundation are aimed at providing objective, independent, and broad-based information on the advantages and risks of new technologies. To this purpose the studies are conducted in collaboration with groups comprised of experts in the relevant fields. The professional expertise of the supervisory groups covers a broad range of aspects of the issue under study.

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